

Perception of Consumers on Purchasing of Home Appliances in Kovilpatti Region

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Abstract

India is an emerging country; in recent times India witnessed a wave of change. Indians literacy levels are improving and Indians demanding better life style, Indian markets have become a global destination for different investors in the world. From the past three decades marketing facing lot of challenges today because understanding the consumers is a comprehensive task because each consumer have different taste and different perception, because customer loyalty have been an integral part due to changing mindset from time to time.

The main aim of the study is to analysis the perception of consumers on purchasing of Home Appliances in Kovilpatti Region. The study mainly based on primary data and data has been collected from consumer co-operatives stores buyers through interview schedule method. The number of members of each region is not uniform. To find the perception and behaviour of consumer on purchasing of home appliances. There are 400 respondents have been selected from kovilpatti region on the basis of the convenience sampling method. This present study can concluded that majority of the consumer profile variables are not associated with reasons for influences of marketing stimuli in purchase of home appliances. Only 5 profile variables are significantly associated in this result such as, Age, education qualification, number of children, monthly income, sources of influence and mode of purchases are associated with the reasons for purchases on home appliance.

Keywords: Buying Behaviour & Perception, Consumers, Home Appliances.

Introduction

In India, especially in all the major cities, every company is trying to stay alive in their platform to their level best in the prevailing condition to achieve the desired level of potential customers. The change in the global economy is inevitable and liberalization plays an indispensable role in our country. The top level multinational Companies have entered into the Indian market and plays an imperative role with their wide and superior range of products. When compared to the world level market Indian market is growing with superior product line in Home appliances. So, it is very significant to the product and we are aware that our “Customer is the King”. In order to achieve the requisite goal in buying the Home appliances, customers are very much conscious and sound enough to take the most appropriate decisions.

Review of Literature

Uma (2014) the study reveals the consumer attitude of Madurai district, the consumers in this place are important part to realize the challenges faced by marketers in comprehending customers mind. Because customer minds consist of different taste, preference, customs, culture, the findings of the study to analyze the consumer buying behavior towards selected home appliances in Madurai, the methodology of the study classified into primary data collected from questionnaires and secondary data from books, magazines. The study came into conclusion that consumer behavior & preference have great impact on home appliances products, the home appliances such as television, air conditioners, washing machines & mixer grinder are used on brand names.

Sai Ganesh & Naveenkumar (2017) the present study assess the buying products various factors will influence to customers such as age, family life cycle, values, attitude, culture, customs because in order analyze the customer likes and dislikes various parameters have been adopted. The study focus on home appliances which are extensively used in Bangalore rural districts, the products are, air conditioner, washing machine, refrigerators, mixer grinder, televisions. The study evaluates location wise consumer buying behavior towards home appliance products in Bangalore rural districts.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows:

- To know the socio-economic background of consumers of purchasing of Home Appliances.
- To evaluate the factors influencing the perception of consumers for Purchasing of Home Appliances in Kovilpatti Region.

Research Design and Methodology of the Study

Sources of Data

The present study is based on both primary and secondary. The primary data were collected from the consumers by meeting them in different places in the study area. For this purpose an interview schedule was prepared. The secondary have been gathered from the survey reports, brochures, journals, magazines, Internet websites and books related to consumer perception on purchasing of Home Appliances.

Sampling Method

Since the population is considering ably large in size it is not practicable to collect data from the whole population within the time frame. The number of members of each region is not uniform. To find the perception and behaviour of consumer on purchasing of home appliances. There are 400 respondents have been selected from kovilpatti town on the basis of the convenience sampling method.

Results and Discussion

In respect of gender of the respondents output inferred that out of 400 respondents, 66.8 per cent of the sample respondents are males and 33.3 per cent of the sample respondents are females.

In the aspect of age of the consumers result exhibits that majority (39.5 percent) are in the age group of 36 – 45 years, 30 per cent are between 26 to 35 years, 17.5 per cent are between 46 to 55 years, 9 per cent are in the age group of above 56 years and the remaining 4 percent are in the age group of up to 25 years.

Marital Status of the respondents result shows that 88.5 per cent of the respondents are married and 11.5 per cent of the respondents are unmarried.

Employment Status of the consumers output express that 187 (46.8%) respondents are private employees, 132 (33%) respondents are government employees, 57 (14.3%) respondents' fathers are businessmen, 16 (4%) respondents are professionals and remaining 8 (2%) respondents belong to others category.

The Factors Influencing Choice of Purchasing Home Appliances

The consumers have used several reasons to evaluate the home appliances goods, quality and warranty whether the goods will be high-quality without default. This section contain 14 statements and the responses are collected from who are brought the durable goods consumers through a structured interview schedule.

Table No.1 Factors Influencing Choice of Purchasing Home Appliances

S.No	Particulars	Mean	S.D	Rank
1	Durability	2.01	0.111	XIV
2	Design	2.31	0.462	XIII
3	Price	2.84	0.367	VII
4	Quality	2.46	0.499	XII
5	Brand Image	2.74	0.439	XI
6	Installation Services	2.78	0.418	IX
7	After sales services	2.94	0.233	VI
8	Customer care	2.83	1.294	VIII
9	Warranty and guaranty	4.44	1.064	II
10	Product variety	4.53	0.993	I
11	Easy of maintenance	2.76	1.404	X
12	Location of the store	3.01	1.336	V
13	Technology	3.41	1.100	III
14	Style	3.13	1.283	IV

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 show that customer feel and expectation that the “Product variety” is the most important factors influencing choice of purchasing home appliances goods. The other reasons also they are give the important such as, warranty and guaranty, technology, style, location of the store. The least important reasons are brand image, quality, design and durability. The consumer will not give more than important.

Relationship between Profile Variable and Reasons for Influences of Marketing Stimuli in Purchase of Home Appliances

This study analyses the relationship between profile variables and reasons for influences of marketing stimuli in purchase of home appliances. For this purpose chi-square, analysis of variance and independent sample t-test are used. There are many profile variables are included in this study.

Table No.2 Relationship between Profile Variable and Reasons for Influences of Marketing Stimuli in Purchase of Home Appliances (Chi-Square)

S.No	Particulars	Chi-square value	Df	Sig
1	Gender	3.715	2	.156
2	Age	27.101	4	.000*
3	Education	32.443	6	.000*
4	Marital status	0.118	2	.943
5	Number of children	11.392	6	.022*
6	Residential type	10.865	4	.093
7	Size of family	4.978	2	.290
8	Type of family	1.142	2	.565
9	Occupation	7.293	2	.113
10	Monthly income	28.243	6	.000*
11	Purchasing decision	8.984	4	.174
12	Sources of influence	22.930	6	.000*
13	Sources of purchases	10.865	4	.174
14	Mode of purchases	25.773	6	.000*
15	Non-availability of favorite goods	4.978	2	.093
16	Most reasons for buying	12.471	6	.056
15	Number of purchases	10.865	6	.290
16	Number visit	9.059	4	.075
17	Number of good experience	5.321	4	.256
18	Number of bad experience	10.805	6	.093

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 presents the level of significance for the chi-square results. If the significant value is less than 0.05 which means the variable are associated. Among 18 variables are included in this study. It is clear that the majority of the consumer profile variables are not associated with reasons for influences of marketing stimuli in purchase of home appliances. Only 5 profile variables are significantly associated in this result such as, Age, education qualification, number of children, monthly income, sources of influence and mode of purchases are associated with the reasons for purchases on home appliance.

Summary and Conclusion

- It is find that most of the respondents fall under the male category.
- It is find that exhibits that among the 400 respondents, 88.5 per cent are the married and remaining of them are unmarried.
- It is identified that 39.5 per cent of the respondents are in the age group between 36-45 years.
- It is observed that 46.8 per cent of the respondents are working in the private sector companies in and around the study area.
- It is captured that consumer feel and expectation that the “Product variety” is the most important factors influencing choice of purchasing home appliances goods. The least important reasons are brand image, quality, design and durability. The consumer will not give more than important.

The study examines the consumer behavior role while considering home appliance such as color television, refrigerators, air conditioners, washing machine, mixer grinders, the analysis and interpretations of the study gives constructive feedback that many customers. This present study can concluded that majority of the consumer profile variables are not associated with reasons for influences of marketing stimuli in purchase of home appliances. Only 5 profile variables are significantly associated in this result such as, Age, education qualification, number of children, monthly income, sources of influence and mode of purchases are associated with the reasons for purchases on home appliance. This study also conveys that consumer feel and expectation that the “Product variety” is the most important factors influencing choice of purchasing home appliances goods. The least important reasons are brand image, quality, design and durability. The consumer will not give more than important.

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